

Using self-confrontation to study user experience: A new approach to the dynamic measurement of emotions while interacting with products

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Abstract:

Measuring emotions experienced while using products with standard psychological tools remains difficult. This paper reviews the available methods and assesses their suitability for design research. It presents a novel approach based on self-confrontation and the results of a first test of this approach. Participants were filmed as they interacted with several different products and reported about their feelings afterwards, while watching the video. Results show that the predicted difference in user experience was reflected in the data collected through this procedure. Potential for further development of the tool is sketched based on these data and on interviews conducted after the test with the participants.

Research about the affective effects of product design is thriving as shown by a number of edited books (Blythe, Overbeeke, Monk, & Wright, 2003; McDonagh, Hekkert, Erp, & Gyi, 2004) and conferences (Design & Emotion since 1999, Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces and Designing for User Experiences since 2003) dealing with this topic. With this trend comes a need for better tools to evaluate the pleurability or more generally the quality and intensity of emotional responses to products. Quantifying the emotions felt by the end-user in a particular product use situation could help evaluate how successful a design is at eliciting the kind of experience it was meant to achieve. Additionally, standard, well-documented measurement tools would greatly help setting up and communicating research on the causes and antecedents of product emotion and on the numerous variables affecting user experience. This paper provides a short review of available methods for the measurement of emotion, both from the field of experimental psychology and from the field of design. After highlighting some of the shortcomings of these tools with respect to design research, a new approach to the measurement of emotion is sketched. This method is specifically geared toward the dynamic assessment of emotional responses during product interaction. The paper continues with a description of the first validation study, carried out to test whether or not a first rough version of the proposed method is able to yield a meaningful measurement of the valence of users' experience with a common everyday product (a vase). The last section discusses the results of this test with an eye for general considerations and practical implications for the assessment of user experience with products.

Review of available measurement tools

The psychological literature described many tools that have been proposed to measure emotion in various ways. Emotion is a complex phenomenon, of which many definitions have been proposed in the last century (Kleinginna, & Kleinginna, 1981). Today, a growing consensus suggests that emotional responses involve the synchronisation of several sub-systems, including conscious feeling, heart and other bodily systems and facial expression (Scherer, 2005). This synchronisation prepares the individual to react appropriately to changes in the environment, ultimately improving chances of survival and reproduction (Cacioppo, & Gardner, 1999). Changes in each of the sub-systems can be leveraged to provide some indications of the emotional processes going on at a given moment. Common measurement tools are based on one

of these components of the emotional response and it is convenient to use these sub-systems to sort them in broad classes and assess the suitability of each of these classes of measurement tools for design research and practice.

The first of these classes of measurement tools is based on changes in behaviour (especially vocal and facial expression) occurring during an emotional response. The study of facial expressions has been instrumental in restoring emotion as a relevant topic in experimental psychology since the 1960s. One of the most influential researchers in this tradition is Paul Ekman. He devised a system to code all visible changes that can be produced by the human face (Ekman, & Friesen, 1978) and described prototypical patterns of facial expression that correspond to basic emotions (Ekman, 1999). These basic “faces” are purported to be universal and automatic (people can merely attempt to “mask” them with limited success but never avoid expressing emotions altogether). Besides being used by researchers to measure emotions in the lab, this framework generated a vast amount of work in the field of affective computing, attempting to build systems capable of automatically recognising the emotions experienced by their users.

Another class of measurement tools is based on the bodily change accompanying any emotional response. Common sense and everyday language teaches us that specific pattern of physiological activity (heart beating stronger, blushing, etc.) are an integral part of our everyday concept of emotion. These reactions have been theorized as providing an evolutionary function to emotion by preparing an individual to adopt an adaptive behaviour in response to perceived challenges and opportunities in the environment. Physiological indicators that have been used for the measurement of emotion include various indicators of respiratory activity (Frazier, Strauss, & Steinhauer, 2004), pupillary response (Partala, & Surakka, 2003) and muscular activity (notably facial electromyography, see Larsen, Norris, & Cacioppo, 2003). However, the most common of these indicators remain skin conductance and heart rate or heart rate variability (Cacioppo, Berntson, Larsen, Poehlmann, & Ito, 2000).

The last class of measurement tools included in this review including many well-known tools. It is based on another central component of an emotional response: the subjective feeling experienced by the individual. These self-report measures of emotion rely on the participant in a

test or experiment to provide themselves a rating of their conscious experience. These ratings can be collected using various scales or questionnaire with verbal or non-verbal (graphical) items. Relevant examples include the Pleasure-Arousal-Dominance scales (Mehrabian, 1996) and the Differential Emotion Scales (Izard, Libero, Putnam, & Haynes, 1993). One of the most widely used of these tools is probably the SAM (Bradley, & Lang, 1994). It is a set of three graphical scales with small characters representing some aspect of affective experience. Each of the scales corresponds to one of the main dimensions of affect underlying the Pleasure-Arousal-Dominance scales.

All of the tools mentioned so far suffer from serious shortcomings when it comes to measuring the emotional response associated with products. First, product emotions tend to be mild and subtle emotions which might escape measurement with standard tools, especially those based on facial expression or physiology. Second, designers need rich descriptions of the experience elicited by their products. Ratings along two or three dimensions or half a dozen basic emotions do not exhaust the phenomenon and other types of data are needed to inform and inspire product design.

The two aforementioned problems limit the usefulness of general emotion measurement tools for product usage situations and warrant the development of specific design-oriented tools. Previous works in that area include PrEmo, developed at the Delft University of Technology (Desmet, 2003). Several aspects of this tool are very relevant to product design and will be reused in the present research. First it includes an extended set of emotions, so as to offer designers more than simply “basic emotion type” data. Second it is based on graphical self-report, which is the best way to get useful information on subtle emotions without depending on participants ability to verbalise their feelings. Indeed, it does not require the knowledge of a particular language and its affective vocabulary. Moreover, instructions are much easier to translate than questionnaire items themselves.

PrEmo, however, was developed to measure user’s response static exposition to a product, typically a short first encounter with it. But product appearance is but one factor of user experience. Product usage is an open-ended, continuous activity, with many factors affecting it

over the course of an interaction. Several strategies for the collection of continuous data about affective experience and meaning have been proposed, especially in the field of music perception (Schubert, 2001) and advertisement research (Stayman, & Aaker, 1993). But in both cases, the stimulus follows a fixed time course and the receiver passively watches or listens to it, leaving him free to report concurrently. On the contrary, in a typical product test, the self-report task and the product itself would be competing for the attention of the user, who cannot be fully involved in both. Currently available tools do not provide any solution to deal with this specificity. This limitation is the starting point of the present research, intended to develop a tool for the measurement of emotion and user experience during interaction with products.

Testing a new approach for the measurement of user experience

The proposed approach includes elements of several of the tools previously described, combining non-intrusive continuous measurement and retrospective self-report. The main innovation compared to other continuous self-report tools is the introduction of self-confrontation, a technique that has been recently applied to human-computer interaction research (Cahour & alii, 2005; Krone, Hamborg, & Gediga, 2002; Lim, 2002) but not to the measurement of emotion. Participants in a test first use the product (or carry out a task) without being interrupted and are videotaped during the interaction. They can report their feelings as they watch this video, immediately afterwards. This self-confrontation approach should allow the collection of meaningful data on the course of experience while limiting interference with the interaction as it happens. Adding the video as cue to the self-report should on the other hand improve the validity of the data compared to a classic retrospective assessment. At a later stage, self-confrontation data on subjective feelings will also be combined with physiological data collected during the interaction.

To assess the viability of this approach, a first prototype of the tool was developed and used in a test with two variants of a product that were expected to elicit different emotional responses in most participants. It was decided that a binary scale (positive/negative) was sufficient for this particular test and that categorical emotions would be integrated later on in the development of the measurement tool. The main hypothesis being tested is that one of these products would elicit a generally more positive experience than the other one and that this difference would be

reflected in the data collected during self-confrontation. Confirmation of this hypothesis would support the idea that the suggested approach is indeed sensitive to moderate differences in product experience. Additionally, interviews of the participants after the test should provide a first assessment of the face validity of self-confrontation as a means to measure emotions.

METHOD

Participants

Participants (N=25) were students at the industrial design faculty of our university. While design students might be expected to react differently to products than the general population, it was decided that this sample was adequate for a first test of the approach. They were approached during the breaks in the free-time area of the building and asked if they would like to participate in a test involving a “new approach to get feedback about peoples’ feelings when using products”. They were paid a small compensation fee to participate.

Materials

Participants were asked to follow a scenario to “test their new digital camera”. They had to “make a nice composition” with some artificial flowers and a vase. Then, they took a picture of it and downloaded this picture on a computer. While such a complex scenario might impede the interpretation of the results, it was needed to create a situation that would come reasonably close to actual product usage to elicit comparable emotions. Yielding useful data in this type of relatively uncontrolled situations (from a scientific point of view) is a sine qua non for a design-oriented tool anyway. Additionally, the scenario added a goal-directed aspect to the task by inviting the participants to make a nice composition to be able to test the digital camera. This task is in line with appraisal theories of emotion (Scherer, Schorr, & Johnstone, 2001) which predict that emotion arise – among other – when an individual is faced with goal-conducive (or, on the contrary, hindering) events.

Two pairs of products were used in the experiment (two different vases and two different cameras). The two vases were chosen so as to elicit different feelings during the use. One of the vases was a small cubic vase made of thick glass (figure 1). The 55 centimetre-long flowers did not fit nicely in it and even tended to fall down, hence making the experience with this vase a

rather frustrating one. The other one was a tall, translucent plastic vase looking like a glass vase (figure 2). It was predicted to be surprising and fun to use, as shown by another research (Ludden, Schifferstein, & Hekkert, 2006).

Figure 1: vase no. 1 (frustrating stimulus)

Figure 2: vase no. 2 (surprising stimulus)

The digital cameras chosen differed in many ways, making prediction regarding the expected experience difficult. We nonetheless decided to use two (instead of refraining from adding an

extra factor in the design) to keep the task interesting and prevent the participants to focus solely on the vase. While the order of presentation could not be counterbalanced in this context, the product combinations the subjects were exposed to were randomised.

Procedure

The test took place individually in our usability lab type facilities. After a short introduction, the participants had to read and approve a consent form. They were then seated at a computer and presented with an on-screen demo of the rating scale they were to use afterwards together with some explanation about the course of the test.

A scenario card was handed out to them and they were asked to read it and wait for the moderator to be ready to record the test. Only then would the actual product test start. The field of the video camera included the table, vase, flowers, camera and computer the participants had to use. The setup resulted in a $\frac{3}{4}$ shot of the participants, from the side. When they finished carrying out the task, the participants had to wait between 1 and 3 min for the video to be saved on the computer before they could start the self-confrontation. The delay depended on the time they used to carry out the task.

The self-confrontation itself took place in the same room, on the computer used before during the introduction. The software was developed specifically for this test and started with a screen reminding the participants of the instructions given to them at the beginning and inviting them to ask any question they might have before starting the self-confrontation (figure 3). After pressing a “start” button the video appeared and the participants could report experiencing a positive or negative feeling at any time until the end of the video. To do so, they had to press one of two buttons (the left “Ctrl” key or the “Enter” key in the numeric keypad). These buttons were situated at opposite ends of the keyboard and were to be operated with a different hand each. Little coloured stickers on the keyboard itself linked the buttons to the two faces on the screen, which were themselves contained in accordingly coloured frames. Following previous tools like the SAM (Bradley, & Lang, 1994) or the 2-Dimensional Emotion Space (Schubert, 1999), a smiling face stood for positive valence (“feeling good about something”) while negative valence was represented by inverting the mouth (going then downwards on both sides, see figure 3).

You are about to see a video of what happened a few minutes ago.

Please remember : just click once everytime you see something on the video that made you feel good or bad. If you have any question, don't hesitate to ask now !

When you are ready, click 'start'

Figure 3: screenshot of the software used for the self-report.

After reaching the end of the video, the software automatically stopped and invited the participant to turn to the moderator. A short interview followed, with four open questions: about feelings during the test, the products in general and then about the feelings and opinions associated with the camera and the vase in particular, in that order. After this interview the participants were handed out the second scenario card and went through the same procedure with the vase and the camera they did not use yet.

After both tasks and self-confrontation sessions were completed, a debriefing interview concluded the test. The moderator queried about the participants' opinion about the software, if

they felt confident they could remember their feelings and finally if they thought this procedure would provide a good way to get feedback on peoples feelings with products.

RESULTS

The data collected were in the form of a list of reports with, for each press of a button, the amount of time since the beginning of the video and the valence (positive or negative) of the experienced feeling. The data from two participants could not be included in the analysis because both of them choose not to put the flowers in the vase in one of the two trials. The number of reports per trial varied widely ($M = 12.72$, $SD = 8.32$) for a total of 636 data points. Additionally, key events in the interaction (first contact with the vase, first attempt to put the flowers in the vase, first contact with the camera) were coded from the video.

Based on these events, all reports recorded in the 8s following the first attempt to put the flowers in the vase were extracted. The 8s delay was chosen somewhat arbitrarily to represent the users first experience in using the vase, our primary interest in this test. Using a fixed “window” (as opposed to the full episode) seemed a simple and efficient way to avoid biasing the results by the time each participant took to complete this subtask. In any case, participants rarely used less than 8s for that.

All reports were then added, giving the weight -1 to negative reports and +1 to positive feelings, yielding two summary ratings (one for each trial, i.e. each vase) per participant. It must be noted that this computation makes impossible the distinction between, for example, “no feelings” (i.e. no report at all) and multiple reports adding up to 0 (i.e. exactly the same number of positive and negative reports).

Still, this simple computation gives an overview of the type of feelings that dominated in the experience of the user. Altogether, participants reported between 0 and 3 times per trials for a total of 22 data points for vase 1 and 19 for vase 2. As shown in table 1, 48% of the participants reported more negative feelings than positive feelings after using vase 1 (predicted to be frustrating) whereas the proportion was inverted for vase 2, with 56% reporting more positive than negative feelings (neutral responses were respectively 44% and 35%). A sign test confirmed

that the difference was significant at the risk level $\alpha=5\%$ ($N=19$, 4 ties, $p=.001$). The sign test provides a simple way to test the significance of this difference, with minimal assumptions. The same scoring procedure was also applied to the whole dataset. Difference was much less marked in this case with 35% negative and 61 % positive reports for the surprising vase and 39% negative and 48% positive feelings for the frustrating vase (the same test was also non-significant, but it would be an error to interpret that as supporting the equivalence hypothesis, especially considering the limited power of the sign test).

Table 1

Overall valence of the feelings reported during the first 8s of use

Valence	Condition			
	Vase 1 (frustrating)		Vase 2 (surprising)	
	No of participants	Percentage	No of participants	Percentage
Negative	11	47.8	2	8.7
Neutral	10	43.5	8	34.8
Positive	2	8.7	13	56.5

DISCUSSION

The results generally support our main hypothesis that meaningful data about user experience can be collected through a self-confrontation procedure. Interestingly, continuous measurement, together with the video, allowed fine-grained analysis of key episodes in this relatively simple scenario. The results described in the previous section would not necessarily be apparent in the data provided by a single overall retrospective rating with a classical measurement tool.

Informal analysis of the interviews carried out after the test also indicates that the method enjoyed a relatively high acceptance from the participants. Nearly all of them were confident they could adequately remember and report about their experience. However, they were also keen to stress several conditions under which they felt this technique should be used. Among them is the

very short delay between the actual test/interaction with the product and the self-confrontation. Many participants also highlighted the importance of the post-test interview to articulate their feelings in more details and provide explanations regarding the reasons they were feeling in a particular way. As expected, many participants also resented the limitation of the self-report to just two possible emotional states (“positive feeling” and “negative feeling”) and expressed the need to be able to report intermediate states and/or qualitatively different feelings.

Combining self-confrontation with continuous and graphical self-report hence seems a promising approach to address some of the limitations of general psychological tools mentioned in the review. Future research should attempt to determine which scales are best suited for design research, and how this measurement relates to outcomes of interest to designers and their clients (such as product attachment, satisfaction, brand loyalty, purchase intent, price willingness, etc.). Other points to explore include the relationship between the data collected during self-confrontation and other approaches (such as retrospective self-report or psychophysiological indicators) and how much these data are influenced by conscious strategies and self-presentation of the respondents.

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